

HYDROTHERMAL AGEING EFFECTS ON VISCOELASTIC AND FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF
GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Durability of glass/epoxy composites during hydrothermal ageing has been analysed. Water effects on the matrix morphology have been investigated by dynamic thermomechanical analysis. Coupling effects between mechanical properties and environment have been studied by static fatigue.

Depending on the hardener composition, the viscoelastic analysis revealed two ageing effects :

-reversible plasticization decreasing the glass transition temperature. This phenomenon depended only on the amount of sorbed water, and has been correlated with Fickian water diffusion.

-temperature dependent hydrolysis of material as revealed by irreversible lowering of T_g and shifts of the master curves to short times. In this case, the water diffusion kinetics exhibited a non fickian behavior.

Ageing induced a drastic reduction of the lifetime under static fatigue in bending mode. Depending on the ageing temperature, the analysis of failure feature revealed two failure mechanisms: a microbuckling mode related to the matrix plasticization and a tensile mode related to fiber and interface hydrothermal damaging.

KEY WORDS: Environmental effect, Epoxy, Glass, Viscoelastic, Fatigue.

1. INTRODUCTION

Structural composites are often exposed to hydrothermic environments in the course of normal service. Thus, the problem of the environmental effects on the durability of composite has been a major concern for several years. Changes in the properties of glass/epoxy composites have often been described by both matrix plasticization or hydrolysis and interface/fiber weakening. The main objective of this study is to differentiate between effects due to matrix and effects due to the reinforcement, by coupling viscoelastic analysis and static fatigue experiments (i.e relaxation). The interaction between water and the epoxy network on the morphological level can be described by means of viscoelastic analysis. On the other hand, static fatigue experiments take into account both morphological changes in the matrix and hydrothermally induced defaults in the glass reinforcement which is known to suffer substantial loss on hydrothermal ageing.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Sample preparation Two different unidirectional S-Glass epoxy composites were selected for this study. Both were manufactured with a high-strength R glass fiber coated with a silane containing sizing.

For the first material (composite 1), DGEBA (CIBA LY556) resin cured with 26 phr DDM (CIBA HT972) was used. Unidirectional plates were obtained by filament winding. Curing cycle was 3 hours at 80°C followed by a 3 hours postcuring at 170°C. Fibre volume fraction was equal to 0.47.

The second material (composite 2) was obtained by moulding unidirectional prepregs tapes from BROCHIER S.A (France).

The matrix was bisphenol A resin hardened by DICY and DDM with tertiary amine as catalyst. The material was cured according to the following schedule: 3 hours at 80°C and one hour at 140°C. Fibre volume fraction was equal to 0.53.

Dimensions of the test specimens are: 1mm x 20 mm x 40 mm or 1mm x 20 mm x 80 mm for sorption experiments; 1mm x 5 mm x 30 mm for DMTA testing; 2mm x 10 mm x 100 mm for static fatigue testing.

Before use, samples were dried during one week at 75°C in a vacuum oven and placed in a desiccator.

2.2 Testing procedures

2.2.1 Sorption experiments Samples were immersed in distilled water at 30°C, 50°C, 70°C and 90°C. A METTLER AE100 analytical balance was used to periodically weigh the specimen within 0.1 mg. Weight gains are expressed in percent of the initial weight.

2.2.2 Viscoelastic analysis Dynamic mechanical measurements were performed in the Polymer Laboratory Mark I DMTA equipped with a bending head. Tests were run with peak to peak oscillation amplitude of 15 μm . Two kinds of experiments were carried out :

- Temperature scans with the aged composite in order to investigate the effects of sorbed water on the thermomechanical properties of the material. A heating rate of 2°C/min and a frequency of 3 Hz were selected. Aged samples have been pasted in an aluminium foil before the test to prevent moisture desorption during the scan.

- Isothermal runs with the aged and subsequently re-dried sample to study the reversibility of the effects of water. The dynamic properties were measured by isothermal steps between 80°C and 200°C. Frequencies were set to 0.1, 0.33, 3 and 10 Hz. Pasted aluminium foil were unable to prevent desorption of the samples during isothermal runs. So, no isothermal experiment was carried out with wet specimens.

Isothermal experiments were used to predict long term viscoelastic behavior of the material. Master curves based on the time-temperature analogy (1) were generated as following. Experimental data at each temperature were plotted on a diagram giving $\log E'$ versus frequency. A reference temperature T_{ref} was selected as the temperature of the maximum drop of $\log E'$ versus frequency. All the isotherms were then horizontally shifted with regard to the reference isotherm in order to generate a single master curve giving $\log E'$ versus frequency.

2.2.3 Static fatigue Monotonic static properties were measured using the normalized three point bending test. A span to length ratio of 20 was selected in order to minimize shear stresses. Specimens were loaded at a 2 mm/min speed, i.e a mean strain rate of 0.128 s^{-1} .

The static fatigue properties ($R = \epsilon_{min} / \epsilon_{max} = 1$) were evaluated using the same conditions. The specimens were characterized at imposed strain on specific test set-ups. The displacement of the loading nose was monitored by a LVDT transducer and the loading was performed at the same rate as in static testing. The stiffness loss was continuously measured by a load cell beneath the loading

nose. The bending cell was designed so that the specimen could be fully immersed during the test. Experiments were carried out :

- in the dried state to establish a baseline for the subsequent study of hydrothermal ageing,

- after 100 days of ageing in distilled water at 30°C, 50°C, 70°C and 90°C. Aged specimens were tested in distilled water at room temperature in order to prevent moisture desorption.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Sorption kinetics Fig. 1 and 2 show the sorption curves obtained when the relative weight gains are plotted versus the square root of immersion time normalised to the thickness h of the sample. Depending on the material, two different behaviors can be noticed.

Figure 1: Sorption kinetics of composite 1 immersed in distilled water
(Solid lines are fitted to Fick's law).

In the case of composite 1, sorption curves increase linearly at first then reach a pseudo-equilibrium state. The weight gain at this pseudo equilibrium is approximately identical for each temperature. This behavior is characteristic of a fickian process, where diffusion is only driven by the water concentration gradient in the material. From Springer's analysis (2), the fickian sorption curves have been computed using the slope of the linear part of the curve and

the weight gain at the pseudo-equilibrium state. At the higher temperatures (70°C and 90°C), positive deviations from fickian law is observed for long times. Micrographs have revealed the occurrence of microcracks which run into the interfacial areas. The above deviations can also be attributed to the water ingress in so hydrothermally induced microcracks.

Figure 2: Sorption kinetics of composite 2 immersed in distilled water
(Solid lines: 40 mm length specimens, dashed lines: 80 mm length specimens).

On the contrary, the second material is characterised by a non fickian behavior over the whole range of immersion time. Continuous increase of weight over the timescale of measurements shows that equilibrium levels are not reached within 1-2 year. Macro-cracking was noticed on micrographs since 30 days of ageing at 90°C. It can be related to the strong positive deviation of the sorption curve at this temperature. Tests were carried out with different specimen sizes, showing an effect of the specimen length on the sorption curves, especially at the higher temperature. Such an effect has been previously reported by Jones et al. (3) for TGDDM/DICY specimens with different widths. This volume effect was considered as resulting from a competition between the leaching of unreacted dicyandiamide along a tortuous path of microcracks and water swelling which allows access to the more polar regions and causes an acceleration in the water absorption.

3.2 Viscoelastic analysis

Both materials have been studied after different immersion times at each of the selected temperatures. Typical $\tan \delta$ spectra in the

glass transition zone are shown in figure 3. The damping peaks are related to the glass transition which is hereafter defined by the temperature T_g of the maximum of $\tan \delta$.

Figure 3: $\tan \delta$ spectra before and after ageing in distilled water at 50°C (3 Hz).

Water ageing results in a shift of the glass transition to the low temperature. This can be attributed to the well known plasticization of the epoxy network by water. These plasticization phenomena are often related to the increase of the free volume of the polymer and to the destruction of intramolecular hydrogen bonds by water molecules (4). Both processes involve an enhanced molecular mobility which in turn induces the lowering of T_g .

The glass transition temperature is linearly related to the $Mt\%$ weight gain until about 0.8% of moisture content for composite 1 or 1.3% for composite 2 (Fig. 4). This linear relationship is independent of the soaking temperature. In order to take into account the difference between fiber contents, the slopes of the $T_g=f(Mt)$ relationships have been calculated in $^\circ\text{C}$ by % of water sorbed by the matrix. Obtained values of $9.8^\circ\text{C}/\%$ for composite 1 and $7.7^\circ\text{C}/\%$ for composite 2 are in good agreement with value reported in other works (5, 6).

At high moisture contents (i.e high temperatures and long immersion times), deviations from the linearity of the $T_g=f(Mt\%)$ relationship can be noticed. That could be due to:

- the filling of the hydrothermally induced voids which leads to an overestimating of the amount of water really sorbed by the network. However, it must be underlined that only water sorbed by the macromolecular network induce changes in the thermomechanical spectra.

-the hydrolysis of the polymer network at high temperatures.

In order to differentiate between these two effects, the reversibility of the changes in the thermomechanical behavior has been investigated by water soaking and subsequent drying of the samples in a vacuum oven at R.T.

Figure 4: Tg versus Mt relationships in distilled water
(composite 2: \square 30°C, \diamond 50°C, \triangle 70°C, \circ 90°C; composite 1: filled symbols)

In the case of composite 1, the thermomechanical properties were totally recovered after desorption of the aged samples, whatever the ageing temperature and for immersion times until 500 days. Thus, the decrease of Tg by water sorption can only be related to reversible plasticization phenomena of the epoxy network.

For composite 2, the changes of the thermomechanical spectra are reversible until a weight gain of approximately 1.2%. Above this moisture content, irreversible changes after re-drying can be noticed on the master curves generated by isothermal runs (fig 5). The first observation is that the master curves show a shift to short times proportional to the ageing temperature.

Moreover, the rubbery modulus decrease with increasing ageing temperature. It is generally admitted that this modulus is related to the average molecular weight between crosslink points (7). Thus, there is some evidence of a decrease in crosslink density by hydrolysis for the DICY containing composite 2.

Figure 5: Master curves for composite 1
before ageing (a); after ageing at 30°C (b), 50°C (c), 70°C (d), 90°C (e).

3.3 Static fatigue

3.3.1 non aged materials Both materials in the non aged state exhibited the same behavior characterized by a sudden drop in the stiffness loss curves. These drastic failures were selected as lifetime criterion. Results for composite 1 have been reported in a S-T diagram representing the imposed strain ϵ_{\max} versus time to failure t_f (fig.6). The beginning of the loading was chosen as the time origin. Hence, it is possible to plot in the S-T diagram the loading curve and the monotonic failure data.

S-T curve of non aged composite 1 is approximately linear in the 0.1-1000 hours range, but surprisingly the extrapolated line does not cross the monotonic failure strain which is a limiting case of static fatigue (failure occurs immediately at the end of the loading). This behavior can be highlighted by the analysis of the failure mechanisms. The failure features were characterized by the microbuckling of the glass fibers on the compressive side of the specimen, just beneath the loading span. Such an effect can be explained by considering stress concentration at loading point, as supported by Berg (8) and Uemura's works (9). Even if this mechanism is not yet fully understood, the static fatigue behavior can be supposed to be related to the local creep of the matrix near the loading point.

Figure 6: S-T curves under static fatigue for composite 1

(■ non aged; aged at □ 30°C, ○ 50°C, △ 70°C, ◇ 90°C; ● monotonic data)

3.3.2 Aged materials After 100 days of water ageing, lifetime reductions and a decrease of the monotonic properties were noticed for both composites.

In the case of material 1, these reductions were independent of the immersion temperature until 50°C (fig.6, Table 1). Conversely, a temperature dependence on time to failure was noticed at 70°C and 90°C. Whatever the immersion temperature, note that weight gains are close to the pseudo-equilibrium (Table 1). This temperature dependence was associated to an evolution of the failure features: After ageing at 30°C and 50°C, failures still occur by microbuckling of the glass fibers; at 70°C and 90°C, the microbuckling mode gives way to a tensile mode on the upper side of the specimen. Similar trends were noticed in monotonic testing.

Whatever the ageing temperature, only microbuckling failure was observed for composite 2.

immersion temperature (°C)	Mt (%)	σ_R (MPa)	ϵ_R (%)
-	dry	1380 (50)	4,0 (0,05)
30	0,8	1140 (30)	3,4 (0,06)
50	0,86	1170 (20)	3,4 (0,06)
70	0,89	1080 (25)	3,0 (0,08)
90	0,94	850 (10)	2,2 (0,03)

Table 1: residual monotonic properties after 100 days ageing in distilled water (composite 1, values in brackets are standard deviations).

Lifetime reductions in microbuckling mode can be highlighted by DMTA results reported before. Related to an enhanced molecular mobility, the plasticization may be expected to result in an increase of the creep ability of the matrix. Making the further assumption that the microbuckling depends on the local creep of the matrix, such a plasticization effect could explain the loss of properties in the microbuckling mode. An attempt has also been made to correlate the loss of mechanical properties to the decrease of the glass transition temperature. For matrix dependant mechanical properties, Chamis et al.(10) proposed to correlate water effects to the glass transition temperature by a power law. From their work and our results, we assumed the following equation to predict residual failure strain in microbuckling mode:

$$\frac{\epsilon_R}{\epsilon_{R0}} = \left(\frac{T_{gw} - TT}{T_{g0} - TT0} \right)^n \quad (1)$$

where

ϵ_R is the failure strain in the aged state,

ϵ_{R0} is the failure strain in the non aged state,

T_{g0} is the T_g of the non aged material,

T_{gw} is the T_g of the aged material,

TT is the test temperature at which ϵ_R was measured,

$TT0$ is the test temperature at which ϵ_{R0} was measured.

n value has been adjusted with monotonic data characterized by microbuckling failure (Fig.7). We found a value of 0.77 which is close to the value of 0.5 obtained by Chamis (10) for the durability of graphite/epoxy composite.

Figure 7: Residual failure strain in microbuckling mode versus adimensional parameter $(T_{gw}-TT)/(T_{g0}-TT0)$. (□ composite 1; ■ composite 2)

In the case of static fatigue, the loss of properties was related to a shift of S-T line to the low strain levels. We noticed that this shift occurred to the same extent than the monotonic failure strain. Thus, it appears that the decrease in endurance properties in static fatigue can also be described by relation 1 and monotonic properties under the same ageing conditions.

As opposed to microbuckling data, monotonic results in tensile mode do not fit relation 1. It is clear that these premature failures involve the nucleation of defects rather than plasticization effects. This behavior can be related to the diffusion controlled weakening of glass fibers and fiber/matrix interfaces. By diffusing through the matrix, water can hydrolyse the silane coupling agent (11) and leach out low molecular weight oligomers.(12). Glass fibers are also known to suffer loss of load bearing ability under moist environments. Metcalfe et al. (13) have proposed a mechanism involving sub-critical crack growth by ion exchange mechanisms between fibers and the surrounding medium.(13).

4. CONCLUSIONS

Viscoelastic analysis of aged materials revealed the occurrence of both reversible plasticization phenomena and irreversible damage processes. Plasticization phenomena were diffusion controlled and associated to a temperature independent linear relationship between Tg and the moisture content. At the opposite, irreversible temperature dependent damaging of the material by either cracking or hydrolysis resulted in deviation from this relationship.

Based on the analysis of failure features, two environmental effects on the static behavior have been identified :

the effects related to matrix plasticization which could be predicted from Tg measurements,

the effects related to the weakening of the fiber and interfaces at elevated temperatures. Further investigations are undertaken to predict these processes.

5. REFERENCES

1. J.D. Ferry, Viscoelastic properties of polymers, third edition, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1980, pp. 264-272.
2. C.H. Shen in G.S. Springer, ed., Environmental effects on composite materials, Technomic Publishing, Co., Inc., Westport, 1981, pp. 15-33.
3. F.R Jones, M.A. Shah, M.R. Bader, International Symposium on Composite Materials and Structure, Beijing, China, 87 (1986).

4. C. Carfagna, A. Apicella, L. Nicolais, J of Applied Polymer Science, 27, 105 (1982).
5. J. Mijovic AND K.F. Lin, J. of Applied Polymer Science, 30, 2527 (1985).
6. P. Peyser and W.D. Bascom, J. of Material Science, 16, 75 (1981).
7. T. Murayama, J.P. Bell, J. of Polymer Science, Part A2, 8, 437 (1970).
8. C.A. Berg, J. Tirosh, M. Israeli, ASTM-STP-497, 206 (1972).
9. M. Uemura, H. Iwai, Proceedings of the French-Japanese seminar on composite materials, Paris, France, 13-14 Mars, 1990, p 1.
10. C.C. Chamis, J.H. Sinclair, ASTM-STP-787, 498 (1982).
11. K.P. Hoh, H. Ishida, J.L. Koenig, Polymer Composites, 11 (3), 192 (1990).
12. Y.T. Liao, Polymer composites, 10 (6), 424 (1989).
13. A.G. Metcalfe, G.K. Schmitz, Glass Technology, 13 (1), 5 (1972).